

MIGRAINE TREATMENT: AMITRYPTILINE IS AN EFFECTIVE, LOW-COST OPTION FOR ATTACKS PREVENTION AND RESTORATION OF QUALITY OF LIFE

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INTRODUCTION

Migraine is a very frequent condition. It is estimated that one-fifth of the world's population suffers from it (Salazar, Berrocal e Failde, 2021), and a similar rate is found in Brazil (SILVA JUNIOR et al., 2012). Furthermore, it is estimated that the disease causes an extensive burden:

when it is related to healthcare and treatment it is called "direct cost"; and when it is related to absenteeism and presentism it is called "indirect cost". In Europe, it is estimated about 7,302,718 euros of total annual cost, both direct and indirect (BADIA et al.,2004). In the USA, such estimative goes about U\$ 1 billion direct costs and U\$ 14 billion indirect costs

(ORHURHU et al., 2021).

Such an important disorder as migraine has attracted attention from pharmaceutical industries, which have invested millions in discovering new drugs for its prevention and take profit from them. The most recent investment has been called Monoclonal Antibodies, and in Brazil, the brands in the health market have their price at about R\$ 1.500,00.

However, there are long-known medicines that have much cheaper prices and are as effective as they. Their broad use has been restricted mainly because of their side effects, which restrain a larger use. But when considering access to treatment, such drugs become much more attractive to societies where the price is the main factor for limitation. Should the adverse effects be avoided, should a major health problem as migraine prevention be solved.

Amitriptyline is one of these medicines, which costs about R\$ 18,00/month in Brazil.

The regular drug industry produces brands that start with 10 mg of the pill, and the medical literature presents average doses of 25-100 mg daily. Such doses are accompanied by collateral effects as weight gain, constipation, xerostomia, dizziness, and somnolence that limit a larger use.

In this paper, the author proposes the use of smaller doses of this drug, which is effective and produces side reactions at a much smaller rate than the doses available at the pharmacies.

METHODS

This study was carried out through a literature review using the most recent bibliography on the subject in question and the search engines Bireme and Scielo.

RESULTS

AMITRYPTILINE:

Chemically, Amitriptyline is a N,Ndimethyl-3-(2-tricyclo [9.4.0.03,8] p e n t a d e c a - 1 (1 5) , 3 , 5 , 7 , 1 1 , 1 3 - hexaenylidene) propane-1-amine (Figure 1). Namely, it is a tertiary amine with a three-ring central structure which means that it belongs to a chemical group known as “tricyclic” (there is another group ijerresearch.org Page | 3 known as “tetracyclic” which has four rings, of course ...) (NATIONAL LIBRARY OF MEDICINE, 2022).

The mechanism of the action takes place by the inhibition of the reuptake of both serotonin and norepinephrine neurotransmitters through the blocking of their transporters (SERT and NET) at the presynaptic terminal of the neurons (TOUR, MARWAHA, 2021). Probably both at the central and at the peripheral pain modulation centers.

It is worth noticing that the adverse clinical problems are dose depended (GILLMAN, 2007). So, this is where lays the window for the use of small doses of the drug for migraine prevention.

Figure 1 Structure of Amitriptyline

Source:
<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/Amitriptyline>

USE:

The usual dose for migraine prophylaxis is about 25 mg/day. The Brazilian Headache Society still sustains the use of Amitriptyline at doses from 12,5-75 mg/day (SOCIEDADE BRASILEIRA DE CEFALÉIA, 2002). But there are references in the medical literature for doses ranging from 2,5 mg to 100 mg/day in adults (DOYLE STRAUSS et al., 2016); and 5-10 mg/day in children (EIDLITZ-MARKUS et al., 2012). Both papers present high rates of success.

At a personal level, this author has been using doses as small as 6-18 mg/day to successfully prevent migraine crises and restore quality of life. They have been manipulated at special pharmacies that produce pills with the required ordered dosage.

CONCLUSION

There is strong evidence both in the medical literature and in the clinical experience to support the proposal of the use of small doses of amitriptyline as an effective, low-cost medication

to prevent migraine attacks. Since migraine has a very heavy health cost, it is possible to achieve great savings with small expenses. The more expensive medicines should be reserved for those who don't present a clinical response at all.

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DIFFUSE LARGE B-CELL LYMPHOMA WITH INFILTRATION OF THE CENTRAL NERVOUS SYSTEM: A CASE STUDY

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<p>1. Master in Public Health - Universidad Columbia Del Paraguay. Specialist in Obstetric Nursing. Graduated in Nursing. Graduated in Psychology.</p> <p>2.. Post Doctorate in Public Health, Administrative Coordinator APAE Niterói, Professor at the IIEP Institute</p>	<p>Abstract Introduction: Non-Hodgkin's Lymphoma can present several subtypes, being the Diffuse Large B Cell Lymphoma (LDGCB) the most common among them, the symptoms are usually: sweating, fever, itching and unexplained weight loss. Objective: Present a case study of LDGCB involving the Central Nervous System. Method: Case report of a patient treated at a high complexity of a University Hospital in the northeast Brazil undergoing chemotherapy and radiotherapy treatment. Results: The literature found confirmed that even with a diagnosis when the disease has an advanced stage, the prognosis is reserved. Conclusion: In this case, the patient died after one year of treatment due to CNS metastasis.</p> <p>Keywords: Central Nervous System. Lymphoma. Metastasis</p>

INTRODUCCION

Cancer is the name given to a set of more than one hundred diseases that have in common a disordered (malignant) growth of cells that invade tissues and organs, which can spread (metastasize) to other regions of the body. (INCA, 2012).

Secondary neoplasms represent an important cause of morbidity and mortality from cancer. With an increase in access and the development of more sensitive diagnostic methods, brain metastases are being diagnosed more frequently. (ONISHI, et al., 2005)

According to Reis, Schwinguel and Nascimento (2003), when the disease is not primary in the CNS, metastases to this site occur in 2% to 15% of cases, in non-Hodgkin lymphoma.

Non-Hodgkin lymphomas (NHL) comprise a heterogeneous group of lymphoid tissue neoplasms with distinct histological subtypes and clinical presentation. In the West, the diffuse large B cell subtype (LDGCB) is the most common. (HALLACK NETO et al. 2005 apud SHIH 1991).

For Bigni (2004), this type of lymphoma represents the fifth most common form in Brazil, with an incidence of 55 thousand cases per year and more than 26 thousand deaths.

Non-Hodgkin's lymphomas are more prevalent in elderly people and males. (MOTA, 2006 apud FERLAY; et al., 2001)

In this context, the aim of this study is to present a case of LDGCB involving the CNS where the main signs and symptoms of brain metastasis are discussed based on a

literature review.

METHODS

The present study dealt with a case report in a High Complexity Oncology Center (CACON) of a University Hospital in the Northeast, which was submitted to chemotherapy and radiotherapy treatment, where the following keywords were used for the research (Lymphoma, Central Nervous System, Metastases), looking for references in databases: Scielo and Bireme.

The study population was the physical and electronic medical record of a patient diagnosed with large B-cell Non-Hodgkin's Lymphoma, seen at the CACON outpatient Clinic.

Data collection took place from February 2017 to April 2018, with prior authorization from the Institution. After the collection period, the data were analyzed based on the theoretical framework studied. O paciente da pesquisa foi estudado de acordo com os preceitos éticos existentes e seu nome mantido em sigilo.

RESULTS

The patient in the study is male, 18 years old, white, single, student, born and resident in Maceió/Alagoas, was admitted to the service through medical referral from another institution, to undergo lymph node biopsy and be accompanied by the hematology team.

His main complaint was back pain, sweating, dark urine and itching in the body, fever, loss of 13 Kg in two months, he brought a result of Cervical Tomography (11/02/17) that showed Lymph Nodes of Dimensions increased in level II, III and IV up to 34 mm; Abdomen and pelvis tomography without contrast (02/11/17), showing a retroperitoneal mass next to the epigastric, increased renal volume with lymph node conglomerates; USG of the Total Abdomen (02/12/17) with result of an enlarged liver, image suggestive of steatosis and nodular image, dilated liver canal and common bile duct, nodular images in hepatic and splenic hila, and nodular image in pancreas topography; and, MRI Upper Abdomen and Cholangio MRI (02/13/17) showing large retroperitoneal lymph node enlargement along the hepatic hilum, Splenomegaly, Nodules in the hepatic parenchyma, splenic and renal pancreatic, Simple cysts in the left kidney, compression of the intrahepatic

and common bile ducts by adjacent lymph node, and nodular configuration in the right lung base.

Physical examination showed lymph node enlargement in the cervical region of approximately 9x4 cm, mobile, painless, without fistulation, absence of inflammatory signs in adjacent skin. Realizado Exames de Análise Clínica e exames para avaliação da função cardíaca.

The patient was submitted to a cervical lymph node biopsy, the result of which was the histopathological study of atypical lymphoid proliferation, consistent with Non-Hodgkin's Lymphoma with characteristics between Burkitt's Lymphoma and diffuse large B-cell lymphoma. (IHC) for confirmation of histogenesis and subclassification. Realizou em 24/02/17 Biópsia de Medula Óssea apresentando 10 espaços intratrabeculares livre de neoplasia e cerca de 80% de celularidade hematopoiética; presença das 3 séries em número habitual e maturação presente.

IHC with result: Bcl2+ Left Cervical Tumor compatible with Large B-Cell Diffuse Lymphoma, stage IV; germinal center. 95% cell proliferative index. CD 20+ CD3-, CD10neg KI67 95% bcl2: +; bcl6+; MuM 1 neg; MYC + 70%.

Chemotherapy treatment started with the CHOP scheme (Cyclophosphamide, Doxorubicin, Vincristine and Prednisone) and 23 sessions of Radiotherapy.

The patient remained under chemotherapy and radiotherapy treatment, evolving with nausea, dizziness, vomiting, intense and persistent headache, 9/10 pain, intermittent visual darkening, intermittent pain in the posterior region of the D leg with heaviness, paresthesia and constipation.

Head CT (06/28/17) was requested, which showed a lesion suggestive of Metastasis to the Central Nervous System (CNS) with perilesional edema and mild midline deviation.

From that moment on, the diagnosis of LDGCB with secondary involvement of the CNS was established.

During the treatment period, he underwent several exams such as: PET/CT; Skull, Thorax, Neck Tomography; Resonance of the Brain, Upper Abdomen; USG Armpit D and Total Abdomen.

Conducted on 03/20/18 Magnetic Resonance and CSF study with confirmation of meningeal progression, since then he says he has been losing stools without feeling, memory impairment and emotional instability. Paciente internou com febre, dores em MMII, que não melhorava ao uso de Morfina e evolui a óbito em 08/04/2018.

Non-Hodgkin's Lymphoma is more common in males, represents between 8 to 10% of all malignant neoplasms in children between 8 and 19 years, and is predominantly due to mature Bcell lymphoma, one of the most common histological subtypes, is diffuse large B-cell lymphoma (LDGCB). (OLIVEIRA; CAMPOS, 2015). The case studied was male, aged 18 years, which is compatible with the studies.

To determine the diagnosis of Non-Hodgkin's Lymphoma, a clinical history is taken, physical examination, imaging and biopsy are performed. The histological type and subtype of lymphoma is determined through histopathological examination associated with immunohistochemistry, and immunophenotyping, immunohistochemistry given the variability of biologically distinct groups of NHL (FERREIRA, 2013).

The approach performed with the abovementioned patient to determine the diagnosis followed what was recommended in several studies, such as clinical history, imaging tests, clinical analysis tests, biopsy and immunohistochemistry. For Saints; Fernandes (2008) to obtain the diagnosis of NHL, it is necessary in addition to clinical history, physical examination and complementary exams, such as: Lymph node/Tissue biopsy; Bone Marrow Biopsy; Immunophenotyping; Blood count; Liquor puncture; Immunoglobulin dosage and imaging exams.

According to the literature, at least 80% of patients with Non-Hodgkin's Lymphoma have palpable lymphadenopathy, mainly cervical lymph nodes. (PETROIANU, 2007) In the present study, the patient had palpable lymph node involvement in the cervical region. For Saints; Fernandes (2008); Mota (2006) the current standard treatment for advanced stages of Diffuse Large B Cell Lymphoma (LDGCB), which is the case of the study above, stage IV, is the CHOP chemotherapy regimen, which was used. These patients should also have their cardiac function evaluated before starting treatment, due to the drug's cardiac

toxicity. Radiotherapy is indicated for the consolidation of those areas that initially presented with a voluminous disease.

Patients with stage IV LDCGB have a poor prognosis. (TILLY, et al. 2003)

This group of neoplasms has a rapid growth rate, so most patients have disseminated disease at diagnosis with involvement of the Central Nervous System, presenting various symptoms such as: fever, adynamia, skin paleness, pale mucosa, change in bowel habits, intestinal obstruction, lymphadenomegaly, pleural or peritoneal effusion, respiratory distress and bone pain. (OLIVEIRA; CAMPOS; 2015)

For Carvalho (s/d) patients undergoing radiotherapy treatment may present clinical complications, with memory impairment and intellectual impairment.

The clinical manifestations of CNS metastases can be general and focal, often several patients have both. Symptoms include headache, cognitive difficulties, personality changes and gait disturbance. (DEANGELIS; WEN; 2015)

Confirming the literature once more, the case studied presented some of the aforementioned manifestations, in addition to alterations in the neurological condition.

Despite advances in the treatment of brain metastases, the prognosis of these patients remains poor, with an overall survival of around 12 months. (SANTOS, et al 2001 apud DAVEY, 1999) In this case, the disease evolution time is consistent with that mentioned in this literature, there was rapid metastatic dissemination of the CNS, and the duration between diagnosis and death was from February 2017 to April 2018.

CONCLUSION

This research aimed to present a case study of a patient with Diffuse Cell Non-Hodgkin's Lymphoma, with involvement of the Central Nervous System, seen in a public hospital, allowing to emphasize how important the clinical evaluation and diagnostic investigation was even in the face of a prognosis reserved.

Despite advances in technology and scientific knowledge about Non-Hodgkin's Lymphoma and its treatment, early diagnosis may be a differential for the

quality of life of patients.

In the hospital context, multidisciplinary work was carried out, which helped and collaborated with the care provided, promoting care, coping with the treatment, minimizing the patient's suffering and promoting emotional support to the family.

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